

SOM 2 (Simplified workflow for 3D model analysis used in Paixão et al. 2024)

This workflow aims to show the step-by-step method to quantify the surface alterations between 3D models, representing the *before* and *after* steps in our experiments, using the software *CloudCompare Version 2.12.3(Kyiv)*. The workflow for 3D model comparison is adapted from (White and Campione 2021)

1. Import
 - a. Import both models (*before* and *after*) as stl. format into the *CloudCompare*.
2. Alignment
 - a. Select both models and align the model using the pair-picking method (use at least 3 common points) and click on align (tools -> Registration -> Align (point pairs picking)).
 - b. Select both models and apply the fine registration to improve the alignment (tools -> Registration -> Fine registration (ICP)).
3. Calculate distances
 - a. Compute the Cloud-Mesh distance (tools -> Distances -> Cloud/Mesh Dist)
 - b. In the computed mesh properties menu verify the “steps” (256 is the default division of the model to calculate the distances)
4. Visualize data
 - a. In the toolbar click on Show Histogram (normally located in the left toolbar menu)
5. Export data
 - a. In the visualization menu of the histogram, click on export as csv.

References:

White, Matt A., and Nicolás E. Campione. 2021. 'A Three-Dimensional Approach to Visualize Pairwise Morphological Variation and Its Application to Fragmentary Palaeontological Specimens'. *PeerJ* 9 (January): e10545. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.10545>.